

2023 CLASSICAL ASSOCIATION CONFERENCE PROGRAMME

[NB: Certain panels begin earlier or continue later than the panel session times specified here. Please check the detailed programme below for further information.]

DAY 1: Friday 21 April 2023	
TIME (BST)	SESSION
10:00am – 10:30am	<i>Registration and Coffee</i>
10:30am – 11:00am	<i>Welcome and Conference Opening</i>
11:00am – 12:30pm	Panel Session 1
12:30pm – 1:30pm	<i>Lunch (local venues)</i>
1:30pm – 3:00pm	Panel Session 2
3:00pm – 3:30pm	<i>Break (refreshments)</i>
3:30pm – 5:00pm	Panel Session 3
5:00pm – 6:00pm	Plenary Lecture: Caroline Vout, University of Cambridge
6:00pm – 7:00pm	<i>Dinner (provided on-site)</i>
7:00pm	<i>Doors open at the Fitzwilliam Museum</i>
7:30pm – 9:00pm	120th Anniversary Celebration of the CA, Fitzwilliam Museum

DAY 2: Saturday 22 April 2023	
TIME (BST)	SESSION
9:00am – 10:00am	Virtual Reality Oracle Presentation
9:30am – 11:00am	Panel Session 4
11:00am – 11:30am	<i>Break (refreshments)</i>
11:00am – 11:30am	Meet the Authors of <i>De Romanis</i> (with Bloomsbury)
11:30am – 1:00pm	Panel Session 5
1:00pm – 2:00pm	<i>Lunch (provided on-site)</i>
2:00pm – 4:00pm	Panel Session 6
4:00pm – 4:30pm	<i>Break (refreshments)</i>
4:30pm – 6:00pm	Panel Session 7
6:00pm – 6:45pm	<i>Reception for Teachers</i>
6:15pm – 6:45pm	Classical Association AGM
6:45pm	Presidential Address: MM McCabe, University of Cambridge/KCL
7:30pm – 8:00pm	<i>Drinks Reception for those attending the Conference Dinner</i>
8:00pm	Conference Dinner and Prizegiving Ceremony

DAY 3: Sunday 23 April 2023	
TIME (BST)	SESSION
9:00am – 11:00am	Panel Session 8
11:00am – 11:30am	<i>Break (refreshments)</i>
11:30am – 12:30pm	Plenary Lecture: Tim Whitmarsh, University of Cambridge
12:30pm – 1:30pm	Photography Exhibition Reception and Prizegiving
12:30pm – 1:30pm	<i>Lunch (provided on-site)</i>
1:30pm – 3:30pm	Panel Session 9

DAY 1: Friday 21 April 2023

10:00am – 10:30am: *Registration and Coffee*

10:30am – 11:00am: *Welcome and Conference Opening*
Lady Mitchell Hall

11:00am – 12:30pm: **Panel Session 1**

Panel 1 – Tragedy in the Modern World

Lecture Block 1

Articulating Classicism: Attic tragedy and the fiction of globalisation

Anna Frieda Kuhn, University of Würzburg

Queering Greek tragedy: the myth of Chrysippus in contemporary poetry, drama and opera

George Sampatakakis, University of Patras

The introduction of Aeschylus' Persae in China: translation, patriotism and the Anti-Japanese War

Mengzhen Yue, Shandong University [online]

Chair: Rosanna Omitowoju, University of Cambridge

Panel 2 – Embodied Narratives in Ancient Art and Ecphrasis

Lecture Block 2

The narrative potential of bodies on Mycenaean inlaid daggers

Rachel Phillips, University of Cambridge

Embodied objects and bodily narrative at Sparta

Daphne Martin, University of Cambridge

Bodies on the brink: the art of suspense in Pseudo-Hesiod's Shield of Herakles

Charlie Pemberton, University of Cambridge

Chair: Paul Cartledge, University of Cambridge

Panel 3 – *Domina* (2021): a Thoroughly Modern Matrona

Lecture Block 3

#MeQuoque: the twenty-first-century Livia in Domina

Lisa Maurice, Bar-Ilan University, Israel

Her dominant hand: the men of Sky's Domina

Monica Cyrino, University of New Mexico

Antigone by any other name? Greek tragic connections in Domina
Anastasia Bakogianni, Massey University, New Zealand [online]

Chair: Emma Stafford, University of Leeds

Panel 4 – Greek Historiography

Lecture Block 4

Plutarch's Quaestiones Graecae and Aristotle's Politeiai: the Megarian cluster (QG 16-18, 59) as Aristotelian fragments?

Carmine Nastri, Università degli Studi di Salerno [online]

Polybius, Plato and histories kata meros

Giustina Monti, University of Lincoln

Pindaric poetry and historiographical λόγος: Herodotus' Corinth

Alessio Ranno, Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa [online]

Chair: Franco Basso, University of Cambridge

Panel 5 – Roman Historiography and Biography

Lecture Block 5

Is Suetonius interested in politics?

Jannis Koltermann, University of Cambridge

Echoes of criticism: Ciceronian allusions in Sallust's Bellum Catilinae

Daniel Sutton, Peterhouse, Cambridge

Dumnorix' mythological madness in Caesar's Bellum Gallicum 5

Jennifer Gerrish, College of Charleston

Chair: Stephen Oakley, University of Cambridge

Panel 6 – Lexicography in the Twenty-First Century: the Cambridge Greek Lexicon

Room G.19

The Cambridge Greek Lexicon

James Diggle, University of Cambridge

The origin and early years of the Cambridge Greek Lexicon

Anne Thompson, University of Cambridge

Chair: James Clackson, University of Cambridge

Panel 7 – Latin Literature of the High Empire

Room G.21

Book 10 of Pliny the Younger's Epistles: an edited account of ideal governance

Matthew Mordue, South Wilts Grammar School

Decolonising the Muses: Statius and the Aedes Herculis Musarum (Silv. 3.1)

Nicolas Liney, Warwick University

Strike my womb! Agrippina the Younger and Seneca's Medea

Elisa Markhoff, Villanova University

Chair: Christopher Whitton, University of Cambridge

Panel 8 – Linguistic and Cultural Interactions

Room 1.02

Greco-Arabic belles lettres

Teddy Fassberg, Tel Aviv University

The date of the Expositio Totius Mundi et Gentium

Richard Westall, University of Dallas (Rome Program)

Numen et Brahman: the power dynamics of Latin translations of Sanskrit texts

Tejas Aralere, University of California Santa Barbara

Chair: Alison John, University of Oxford

Panel 9 – The Politics of Reception

Room 1.11

Femininity, domesticity and the Roman statesman in early eighteenth-century Britain

Jessica Glueck, University of Cambridge and University College School

The epigraphical is political: Corpus Inscriptionum Etruscarum and the politics of German classical scholarship 1885-1936

Annie Burman, Uppsala University

Padania, 'Celtic' identity and anti-Roman narration in Italian political discourse (1996-2001)

Giovanna Pasquariello, University of Edinburgh

Chair: David Scourfield, Maynooth University

12:30pm – 1:30pm: *Lunch (local venues)*

1:30pm – 3:00pm: **Panel Session 2**

Panel 10 – Ancient Letter Collections: Structure, Narrative and Belatedness

Lecture Block 1 – NB: This panel will begin at 1:00pm.

Two epistolary cultures? Reading divergence between Greek and Latin letter collections
Roy Gibson, Durham University, and Andrew Morrison, University of Glasgow

Cicero, Ad Quintum fratrem: a Ciceronian microcosm
Laura Losito, Durham University

Seneca's amici: the Epistulae Morales on friendship and growing old
Janja Soldo, University of Edinburgh

'Future me problems': belatedness in ancient epistolography
Julene Abad Del Vecchio, University of Manchester

Chair: Catherine Steel, University of Glasgow

Panel 11 – The Maternal in Antiquity: Interdisciplinary Reflections

Lecture Block 2

Ananke and her daughters
Tuhin Bhattacharjee, New York University

Lectio philosophica and the philosophy of the tragic: theatrical scenarios towards a metanoia of care
Alessandra Filannino Indelicato, University of Milano-Bicocca

Pandora's Box: mothers, monsters and androids in antiquity
Agnibha Banerjee, Rice University

Chair: Alessandra Filannino Indelicato, University of Milano-Bicocca

Panel 12 – (De)/(Re)-Constructing Race in the Ancient Mediterranean World: Perspectives from the Margins of 'Classics'

Lecture Block 3 – NB: This panel will begin at 1:00pm.

Empire and its Others in Petrarch's Africa
Samuel Agbamu, University of Reading

Nuances of reclamation and racialisation: rethinking black and brown faces in new spaces
Lylaah Bhalerao, Institute for the Study of the Ancient World (ISAW), New York University

A white man in Minnesota, an Athenian in Atlantis: race in Platonic mythmaking
Ashley Lance, University of Cambridge

The Age of Hunters to the Age of Commerce: a racial reading of James Barry's The Progress of Human Culture and Knowledge

Hardeep Dhindsa, British School at Rome

Chair: Samuel Agbamu, University of Reading

Panel 13 – Philosophy at Rome

Lecture Block 4 – NB: This panel will begin at 1:00pm.

Papirius Fabianus: philosopher or declaimer?

Zakarias Gram, University of California, Los Angeles

Virgil's Carthage and the Epicurean harbour of philosophy

Nicholas Freer, University of Iceland

Societatem caritatis coire: the union of duty and desire in Cicero's philosophical treatises

Laurie Wilson, Biola University

Fog in Seneca's Naturales Quaestiones: cataclysms and natural philosophy

Florence Rogers, University of St Andrews

Chair: Malcolm Schofield, University of Cambridge

Panel 14 – Human and Divine in Greek Art and Archaeology

Lecture Block 5

'Much new to an European eye': reassessing the representation of local populations in the archaeological landscape of Ottoman Lycia

Seb Marshall, University of Cambridge

Hermes and Aphrodite on the Parthenon Frieze: human-divine interaction

Ellie Mackin Roberts, King's College London

Cognitive approaches to the geranos dance: emotional regulation, visual exclusivity and the embodied experience of Athenian pasts on Delos

Ben Stanley Cassell, King's College London

Chair: Nigel Spivey, University of Cambridge

Panel 15 – Pedagogy: Past, Present and Future

Room G.19 – NB: This panel will begin at 1:00pm.

Gazing at the future: metaverse and the teaching of Classics through virtual, augmented and mixed reality

Antony Makrinos, Department of Greek and Latin, UCL

Humanistic literature in the classroom using the example of Praise of the City of Stralsund by Zacharias Orthus

Frank Lembke, Nikolaus Lenau Lyceum Timisoara [online]

Legit Classics: a podcasting approach to making the classics more accessible

Jasmine Elmer

Χαρτοφυλάκιον/Scrinium: an integrating activity for classical language learning

Sofia Villegas-Rodríguez, Universidad de La Sabana [online], Fernando Alexander Calderon-Velasco, Universidad de La Sabana [online], and Ronald Forero-Álvarez, Universidad de La Sabana

Chair: Rebecca Coe, Hitchin Girls' School

Panel 16 – Alternative Receptions

Room G.21

A human ass, vine women, and a nation of trees: understanding otherness from Apuleius and Lucian to Holberg and Achebe

Eleni Bozia, University of Florida

The use of classical model(s) in graffiti and street art

Anna Socha, University of Liverpool [online]

Dionisa travesti: a Mexican trans Bacchae

Oliver Baldwin, University of Reading

Chair: Tori McKee, Hughes Hall, Cambridge

Panel 17 – Greek Literature and Thought

Room 1.02

Socrates and the development of exemplarity

Roger Brock, University of Leeds

Luxury automated Lemnian gynο-communism: Polyxo in Apollonius' Argonautica

Alastair Daly, Trinity College Dublin

The rhetoric of Paul and Plato: reading 1 Corinthians 12:12-31 alongside the Republic

Sungjoo (Jonathan) Kim, Calvin Theological Seminary

Chair: Frisbee Sheffield, University of Cambridge

Panel 18 – Aspects of Ancient Linguistics

Room 1.11

Endangered writing systems ancient and modern: using the example of the wider classical world to develop strategies for maintaining present-day cultural heritage

Pippa Steele, University of Cambridge

Not only verba activa and verba passiva: the ambiguity of genders between boundaries

Maria Camilla Mastriani, Università degli Studi di Napoli 'Federico II' and Sorbonne Université [online]

Odd Greek writing style and the Septuagint

Timothy Lee, University of Cambridge

Chair: James Clackson, University of Cambridge

3:00pm – 3:30pm: *Break (refreshments)*

3:30pm – 5:00pm: **Panel Session 3**

Panel 19 – Greeks, Romans and Jews

Lecture Block 1

A new look at Jews in the Roman army during the Jewish revolts
Haggai Olshanetsky, University of Basel [online]

Greek language and Hellenistic Jewish identity: the example of 3 Maccabees
Ryan Comins, University of Cambridge

'Aseneth': a biblical romance for Classicists
Anthony Sheppard, British Institute at Ankara

Chair: Julia Snyder, University of Cambridge

Panel 20 – Sicily in its Mediterranean Context

Lecture Block 2

The archaeology of the Punic Wars: insights from Pantelleria and Western Sicily
Carrie Ann Murray, Brock University

The economics of politics: the imperial relationship between the res publica and Sicily
Giuseppe L. Ficocelli, Institute of Classical Studies

Athens around the globe: local reflections of classical Athenian rhetoric in Syracuse and beyond
Edward Armstrong, University of St Andrews

Chair: Alessandro Launaro, University of Cambridge

Panel 21 – New Perspectives on Ancient Greek Geography

Lecture Block 3

The measure of the earth: making a microcosm in Agathemerus' Sketch of Geography
Daniel Hanigan, University of Cambridge

Networked nations and travelling texts: geography and translation in the Letter of Aristeas
Oliver Parkes, University of Cambridge

Linguistic grounds for revising the date of the Periplus of Hanno
Grant Kynaston, University of Cambridge

Chair: Anna Lefteratou, University of Cambridge

Panel 22 – Sophocles

Lecture Block 4

‘The cause of these troubles’? Paris at Sophocles Philoctetes 1426

Brian McPhee, Durham University

The meaning of the body in Sophocles’ Electra

Afroditi Angelopoulou, University of Southern California

‘The same soul-blasts of the same winds’: wind and madness in Sophocles’ Antigone

Danchen Zhang, University of Warwick

Chair: Douglas Cairns, University of Edinburgh

Panel 23 – The Second Sophistic

Lecture Block 5

‘A beauty not human but divine’: wonder, belief and fiction in Chariton’s Callirhoe and its early reception

Claire Rachel Jackson, Ghent University

The affect of a Pergamene aqueduct: Aelius Aristides’ Oration 53

Artemis Brod

Matronymics at work: female succession techniques in Lucian’s Dialogi Meretricii and some early Thecla literature

Dawn LaValle Norman, Australian Catholic University

Chair: Rebecca Laemmle, University of Cambridge

Panel 24 – When Classicists Enter the Policy Arena

Room G.19

Sharing Classics research with policymakers: why bother?

Arlene Holmes-Henderson, Durham University

Implementing the Latin Excellence Programme: an update

Charles Furber, Future Academies, and Emma Palmer, Future Academies

Developing an evidence-informed education profession in Wales: collaborative approaches to language-based research

Ellen Bristow, Cardiff University

Chair: Arlene Holmes-Henderson, Durham University

Panel 25 – Models of Monarchy

Room G.21

Anxiety and incompetence: Spartan relationships with monarchs in the Peloponnesian War

Daniel Unruh, Institute of Continuing Education

Female rulers, the political body and the doctrine of capacities

Danny Pucknell, Cardiff University

Royal women, armies and warfare in Hellenistic Iran: who had more power?

Ana García-Espinosa, Cardiff University

Chair: Shushma Malik, University of Cambridge

Panel 26 – Greek Oratory and Democracy

Room 1.02

Kairos and public policy in Demosthenes' political oratory

Ifigeneia Giannadaki, University of Florida

Power in the undemocratic assembly

Tim McConnell, University of Leeds

'We, your advisors, are responsible, you, our audience, not so': fifth-century Athenian responses to voter irresponsibility

Daniel Tang, King's College London

Chair: Giulia Maltagliati, Clare Hall, Cambridge

Panel 27 – Cultural Stereotypes between the Romans and the Others

Room 1.11

'Vince animum': Roman virtues and Numidian vices in Livy's portrayal of Masinissa

Jasmin Lukkari, University of Helsinki

The Greek Other in the satirical poems of Martial

Joonas Vanhala, University of Turku

Us and them: cultural stereotypes between the 'East' and the 'West' from the fifth to the ninth century

Maria Jokela, University of Turku

Chair: Cédric Scheidegger-Laemmle, University of Cambridge

5:00pm – 6:00pm: **Plenary Lecture**
Lady Mitchell Hall

Firing the canon: Greek and Roman art illuminated
Caroline Vout, University of Cambridge

6:00pm – 7:00pm *Dinner (provided on-site)*

7:00pm *Doors open at the Fitzwilliam Museum*

7:30pm – 9:00pm **120th Anniversary Celebration of the Classical Association**
Fitzwilliam Museum

DAY 2: Saturday 22 April 2023

9:00am – 10:00am: **Virtual Reality Oracle Presentation**
Little Hall

Following the presentation, and for the rest of Saturday and Sunday, the Virtual Reality Oracle will be available for testing in **Room 2.03**. Conference attendees will have the opportunity to experience the virtual reality headsets and the Dodona Oracle, in small groups.

To book your timeslot, please follow the link on the 'Programme' webpage (www.classics.cam.ac.uk/seminars/classical-association-conference-2023/programme).

9:30am – 11:00am: **Panel Session 4**

Panel 28 – Pedagogy and Inequalities

Lecture Block 1

From silence to self-representation: Roman women in the classroom
Andrea Basini, Liceo Pasteur, Rome

Class, Calypso and Coventry
Stephanie Hamman, Eden Girls' School, Coventry

The Athena Society: teaching gender equality through Classics, history, politics, literature and art
Laura Aitken-Burt, Emanuel School

Chair: Mollie Legg, Chesterton Community College

Panel 29 – New Approaches to Teaching

Lecture Block 2

'Not Cicero again': the case for Late Antiquity in the Classics classroom
Stephen Belfield, Berkhamsted School

Lessons from the pandemic: an approach to project-based learning for A Level Classical Civilisation
Rob Hancock-Jones, Townley Grammar School

First-day texts: a year-long approach to promoting a sense of belonging in Advanced Latin classes
Benjamin Joffe, The Browning School (New York City)

Chair: Charles Weiss, University of Cambridge

Panel 30 – Ovid and Beyond

Lecture Block 3

More than absence: Ovid and exile in Seneca's Hercules Furens

Elaine Sanderson, University of St Andrews

Trees and the city in Fasti 3

Charles Ham, Grand Valley State University

Ecopsychology and Ovid's Metamorphoses

Emily Lord-Kambitsch, Pacifica Graduate Institute

Chair: Roy Gibson, Durham University

Panel 31 – Issues in Greek Philosophy

Lecture Block 4 – NB: This panel will continue until 11:30am.

Anaximander without the Apeiron: making sense of Aristotle's and Theophrastus' Reports

Pavel Hobza, Palacký University Olomouc, Czech Republic

Why nutritive and generative soul are the same in De Anima 2.4

Kyosuke Katada, University of Cambridge

Plato's 'Aristippus Problem': the greatest weakness of Plato's project on pleasure

Georgia Mouroutsou, King's University College and Western University, Canada

Plato's concept of justice in Greek literature

Braelyn Smith, Villanova University

Chair: Nicholas Denyer, University of Cambridge

Panel 32 – Beyond Quizlet and Kahoot! Teaching Classics Using Digital Technology: Practices, Developments and Ideas for the Future

Lecture Block 5

Assassin's Creed: Odyssey in the classroom

Alastair Thorley, Stockport Grammar School

Adaptive teaching and the use of digital parsing tools

Rebecca Coe, Hitchin Girls' School

Tufts University Digitising Life in the Roman World: critical design notes for KS3 classroom activities

Jane Ainsworth, University of Leicester, and Marie-Claire Beaulieu, Tufts University [online]

Chair: Steven Hunt, University of Cambridge

Panel 33 – Classics in Art and Cartoons

Room G.19

The art market in Rome in the late nineteenth century: a focus on the Archivio del Commercio, Belle Arti, Industria, Agricoltura e Lavori Pubblici (ASR) as a source for the history of the Wilshere Collection and other collections of early Christian art and inscriptions

David Rini, University of Reading and Ashmolean Museum, University of Oxford

The COVID-19 crisis in political cartoons inspired by classical myth, ancient sculpture and historical figures: a case-study in classical reception

Alexandre Mitchell, University of Fribourg

Roman imperial pop art: replication, reproduction and reception in Les Aventures de Jodelle

Savannah Sather Marquardt, Yale University

Chair: Albert Bates, Sidney Sussex College, Cambridge

Panel 34 – Otherness in Ancient Greece

Room G.21

The power dynamic of the author–source relationships in Herodotus’ Histories

Juha Isotalo, University of Turku

Blaming and self-claiming – two sides of otherness in magic

Saara Kauppinen, University of Helsinki

The realness, strangeness or familiarity of things past? Some recent shifts in the discourse on the otherness of ancient Greek societies

Eddie Jones, Balliol College, Oxford

Chair: Robin Osborne, University of Cambridge

Panel 35 – Representations of War and the Military

Room 1.02

Frontinus’ Stratagems and the ethics of military discipline

James Chlup, University of Manitoba

Lives in parallel: representing late republican civil war before and after the Year of the Four Emperors

Elisabeth Slingsby, University of Cambridge

Behind the rise of Odenathus and Zenobia: Palmyrene military identity in the Roman Near East

Lila Knight, Durham University

Chair: Daniel Sutton, Peterhouse, Cambridge

Panel 36 – Ancient Place and Space

Room 1.11

Hasn't the world changed? The significance of recycling ethnographic tropes in Late Antiquity
Cedrik Michel, Durham University

Remembering the dead on the edge of empire: epitaphs and emotional communities in late antique Milan
Meghan Dulsky, University of St Andrews

Sailing through space: archaeology and the lived space of ancient ships
Rowan Munnery, University of St Andrews

Chair: Ian Morris, Stanford University

11:00am – 11:30am: *Break (refreshments)*

11:00pm – 11:30pm: **Meet the Authors of *De Romanis* (with Bloomsbury)**
Little Hall

11:30am – 1:00pm: **Panel Session 5**

Panel 37 – Sanctuaries and Space

Lecture Block 1

In pursuit of purity: the recurrence of demolition and eviction in central Rome during the Augustan and Fascist periods

Zoe Fox, University of Birmingham

Monumentalising sanctuaries in central Italy: local interests and 'global' Mediterranean connectivity in a diachronic framework

Luca Ricci, University of Oxford

The feminine perspectives inscribed on lead: women's consultations at the Oracle of Dodona

Karolina Frank, University of Warsaw

Chair: Eóin O'Donoghue, Brandeis University

Panel 38 – New Approaches to Metre

Lecture Block 2 – NB: This panel will continue until 1:30pm.

Stacking: Repetitive metrical position in the Greek Hexameter

Stephen Sansom, Florida State University

Phonetic units and cola in the lyric metres of Greek drama

Daria Kohler (Kondakova), KU Leuven

Metre and narrative in lyric poetry: Sappho, Alcaeus, Horace

Il-Kweon Sir, University of Cambridge

Porphyrio and Ps.-Acro on metre and structure in Horace's Epodes and Odes

Antonina Kalinina, University of Oxford [online]

Chair: Matthew Ward, Christ's College, Cambridge

Panel 39 – *Caecilius in Hortō Manet*: Exploring the Past, Present and Future with the Cambridge Latin Course

Lecture Block 3 – NB: This panel will continue until 1:30pm.

Fābula mīrābilis: a narrative story

Lisa Hay, Cambridge School Classics Project

Going beyond 'the fun bit at the end of each chapter': meaningful teaching of Roman civilisation in the Key Stage 3 Latin classroom using the CLC fifth edition

Lottie Mortimer, Cobham Free School and University of Sussex

On sensitivity reading: the what, how, and why

Pria Jackson, Princeton University [online]

Using the CLC fifth edition in the classroom: students' responses to new stories

Joanna Johnson, Solihull School [online]

Chair: Caroline Bristow, Cambridge School Classics Project

Panel 40 – Reading (not Translating) Latin: Classroom Strategies that Everyone Can Use

Lecture Block 4 – NB: This panel will continue until 1:30pm.

Reflections on reading in Latin

Polly Philp, Emanuel School, Wandsworth

Predicting the meaning of Latin narratives through contextual clues

Matthew Mordue, South Wilts Grammar School

Extensive reading in practice

Melissa Cooper, Royal Masonic School for Girls

Pre-reading for fluency, understanding and stylistic awareness

Rachel Plummer, Rugby High School for Girls

Chair: Steven Hunt, University of Cambridge

Panel 41 – The Septuagint within Post-Classical Greek

Lecture Block 5

Separated souls and a sea full of snakes in Greek Genesis

Tyler Horton, University of Cambridge

Verbal periphrasis with ποιέω in the Septuagint and post-Classical Greek

Marieke Dhont, University of Cambridge

Jewish case alternation? Variation in the Greek Pentateuch and post-Classical Greek

Robert Walker, University of Cambridge

Chair: Max Leventhal, University of Cambridge

Panel 42 – Ancient Wisdom Discourse

Room G.19

Configuring moral authority in Greek archaic poetry

Sara De Martin, Regent's Park College, Oxford

Rethinking the tension between wisdom and a 'wisdom discourse' within the Classical-biblical dialectic

Anna Lucia Furlan, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Milan

(Un)exemplary teaching in Boethius' De Consolatione Philosophiae

Katherine Krauss, Australian Catholic University [online]

Chair: Christopher Rowe, Durham University

Panel 43 – Ancient Voices

Room G.21 – NB: This panel will continue until 1:30pm.

'Filling the hands': a Semitist's perspective on fostering linguistic breadth

Nathaniel Greene, University of Aberdeen [online]

Through the ages: Latin and lifelong learning

Alison Greer, University of Glasgow

Who's like us? Using ancient voices to build a modern community

Alex Imrie, Classical Association of Scotland

Ancient voices

Sam Newington, University of Aberdeen

Chair: Sam Newington, University of Aberdeen

Panel 44 – Growing Classics via Innovative and Inclusive Pedagogies

Room 1.02

Queering the past(s): using Classics in schools

Nancy Rabinowitz, Hamilton College

Growing Classics via museum partnerships

Peter Swallow, Durham University

Opening up the curriculum: rethinking myth, access and EDIfication at the Open University

James Robson, Open University

Chair: Arlene Holmes-Henderson, Durham University

Panel 45 – Pedagogical Practice: Classics and Cognition

Room 1.11

What Classics A Level offers beyond a qualification

Alastair Thorley, Stockport Grammar School

Ensuring all learners maximise their potential: how cognitive science can be applied practically within the Classical classroom

Francesca Grilli, Runshaw College

What's the story? Using narrative to teach scholarship in A Level Classics and Ancient History

Danny Pucknell, Cardiff University

Chair: Cora Beth Fraser, Open University

1:00pm – 2:00pm: *Lunch (provided on-site)*

2:00pm – 4:00pm: **Panel Session 6**

Panel 46 – Reception: Modern Legacies

Little Hall

Housman and the Dutch

Bram van der Velden, University of Groningen

Blindness and Classical Studies in the twenty-first century

Jason Morris

The presence of Virgil's Eclogues and Georgics in Luís de Camões' Os Lusíadas

Miguel Ângelo Andriolo Mangini, University of São Paulo [online]

Mithraic Studies in the contest for Iranian identity

Nina Mazhjo, Wrocław University [online]

Chair: Maya Feile Tomes, University of Cambridge

Panel 47 – Materiality, Textuality, Identity: Recent Research at the British School at Rome

Lecture Block 1

Connectivity, space and identity between Roman Sicily and South Italy

Jessica McKenzie, Macquarie University [online]

The gladiatorial graffiti of the Roman amphitheatre: a new contextual perspective

Alessandra Tafaro, University of Macerata

Is there a Roman Metaponto? Reflections about its territorial and maritime aspects

Marc Duret, University of Geneva

The ruins of the Third Rome: negotiating the legacy of Fascist Italy's Empire

Samuel Agbamu, University of Reading

Chair: Emlyn Dodd, British School at Rome

Panel 48 – From Plato to Proclus

Lecture Block 2

Proclus' proof for the immortality of the soul in the Elements of Theology

Rares Marinescu, University of Cambridge and KU Leuven

We don't need no education: the significance of philosophical inclusivity in Epicurean theology

James Stevenson, University of Exeter

Seeing-yet-unseen: Gyges, Er and the necessity of the estranged in Plato's Republic

Keren Freidenreich, The Graduate Center, CUNY [online]

Aristotle's individuals and the frothy bubble

Zuri Biringer, University of Cambridge

Chair: Lea Niccolai, University of Cambridge

Panel 49 – Amarantus and his Neighbourhood: an Innovative Multidisciplinary Approach to KS3 Classics and (Ancient) History Pedagogy

Lecture Block 3

The archaeology of Amarantus and his neighbourhood

Sophie Hay, Archaeological Park of Pompeii [online]

Amarantus, a worthy prequel to Caecilius? Writing a new Pompeiian adventure

Caroline Lawrence, author of the *Roman Mysteries*

Illustrating the Amarantus Project

Laura Jenkinson-Brown, illustrator of Greek Myth Comix and teacher, Churcher's College

Classics in the Curriculum, a Trojan horse: pedagogical thinking behind the Amarantus and his neighbourhood teaching scheme

Caroline Bristow, Cambridge School Classics Project

Chair: Mair Lloyd, Cambridge School Classics Project

Panel 50 – Mythotopia: Web-Based Learning and Innovative Approaches to Myth

Lecture Block 4

The use of Mythotopia as a tool of web-based learning in Greek higher education

Artemisia Archontogeorgi, Democritus University of Thrace and secondary school teacher, Chrysovalantis Sitsanis, Democritus University of Thrace, Ioanna Laftsi, Democritus University of Thrace [online], Charilaos N. Michalopoulos, Democritus University of Thrace, and Andreas N. Michalopoulos, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens

Hanging out with ... a myth! Promoting social and emotional learning through myth

Andriani Liatsopoulou, Democritus University of Thrace and secondary school teacher, Petros Tzimas, secondary school teacher, and Anna Mastrogrianni, Democritus University of Thrace

Orpheus' Thrace: drawing the links between mythical place and character in web-based learning in the Greek high school

Maria Papapanagiotou, Democritus University of Thrace and secondary school teacher, Maria Nikolaidou, Democritus University of Thrace, and Ioannis Deligiannis, Democritus University of Thrace

The use of Mythotopia in extra-curricular primary education

Krystalia Chourmouzei, Democritus University of Thrace, and Maria Georganta, Democritus University of Thrace

Chairs: Ioannis Deligiannis, Democritus University of Thrace, and Charilaos N. Michalopoulos, Democritus University of Thrace

Panel 51 – Classics in Caledonia

Lecture Block 5

The strange story of Classics education in Scotland: a paradox of policy and practice

Arlene Holmes-Henderson, Durham University

Bruce and the spider: the fight to return Classics to Scotland's classrooms

Alex Imrie, Classical Association of Scotland

Beyond the wall: keeping Classics alive in Scottish state schools

Lucy Angel, Mackie Academy

'Not for the likes of us': breaking down access barriers in the Scottish Classics classroom

George Connor, Monifieth High School

Chair: George Connor, Monifieth High School

Panel 52 – Homer and his Reception

Room G.19

Achilles' fable of oaths and concord: a study of the simile at Iliad 22.262-6 and its interrelationship with animal fable and folklore

Lucilla Crespi, University of Edinburgh

'Lies like true things': poetry, power and panhellenism in archaic Greece

Frances Pickworth, University of Bristol

Achilles' destiny in the Iliad

Franco Basso, University of Cambridge

Rousing the thumos with speech: Martial and domestic motivations of the Homeric thumos

Emily Reason, University of Nottingham

Chair: Richard Hunter, University of Cambridge

Panel 53 – Christian Reading, Writing and Performing in the Roman Context

Room G.21

Epistolary fiction among early Christian authors: 1, 2, 3 John as Graeco-Roman fictive letters?

Elizabeth Corsar, St Padarn's Institute, Cardiff

Fatal charades and the martyrdom of Perpetua

Sarah Parkhouse, University of Manchester

Variations of Christian pseudepigraphy in their wider cultural context

Kimberley Fowler, University of Groningen [online]

Chair: Mark Humphries, Swansea University

Panel 54 – Early Intervention: the Case for Primary Classics

Room 1.02

Mike Beer, University of Exeter and Devon and Cornwall Network Coordinator, Classics for All

Anna Bell, London and South-East Network Coordinator, Classics for All

Angela Dix, East of England Network Coordinator, Classics for All

Hilary Hodgson, Classics for All

Chair: Hilary Hodgson, Classics for All, and Hannah Walsh, Classics for All [online]

Panel 55 – Women’s Learning and Learned Women in Roman Antiquity

Room 1.11

Republic of women’s letters? Female learning in the second and first centuries BCE

Olivia Elder, University of Oxford

Writing (to) learned women in Pliny and Seneca

Caitlin Spencer, Durham University

Bilingual learning and its uses among women in Late Antiquity

Alison John, University of Oxford

Women who count: matronae, marriage and mathematics in Late Antiquity

Ella Kirsh, Brown University

Chair: Talitha Kearey, St John’s College, Cambridge

4:00pm – 4:30pm: *Break (refreshments)*

4:30pm – 6:00pm: **Panel Session 7**

Panel 56 – Aspects of Augustanism

Little Hall

Dynastic power and civic freedom in the transition from Republic to Principate: two-level sovereignty revisited

Bradley Jordan, University of Oslo

Augustan marriage legislation in Augustan inscriptions: signs of persuasion?

Chingyuan Wu, Peking University

Triumvir or tyrant? Intertextuality with Augustus' Res Gestae in Minor Declamation 267

Kirsten Parkin, University of Cambridge

Chair: Stephen Oakley, University of Cambridge

Panel 57 – Classics in Novel and Film

Lecture Block 1

Dystopian gladiators: the young adult literary phenomenon and its critique of arena spectacles

Hebe Barlow, University of Birmingham

'A little beyond human': expanding the conceptualisation of the human subject in Carson's Autobiography of Red

Jewel Oreskovich, University of Western Australia [online]

Comparative insights into Apuleius' Golden Ass and Robert Bresson's Au Hasard Balthazar

Simon Smets, University College London

Chair: Tim Whitmarsh, University of Cambridge

Panel 58 – Stepping into the Past: Using Virtual Reality in the Classroom to Bring the Ancient World to Life

Lecture Block 2

Engaging schools with VR – the experiences of the Warwick Classics Network

Paul Grigsby, University of Warwick

The use of immersive virtual reality in the secondary Classics classroom

Tom Johnson, Stephen Perse Foundation

Minecraft and VR in the classroom

Philip Harper, Loughborough Grammar School

Chair: Rachel Plummer, Rugby High School for Girls

Panel 59 – Aspects of Pedagogy

Lecture Block 3

Teaching diverse sources in the Latin classroom: a case study of CIL iv.5296

Bartolo Natoli, Randolph-Macon College [online]

Consent in Classical Civilisation GCSE

Joanne McNamara, Liverpool College

Avoiding pseudo-archaeological assumptions at KS3

Laura Jenkinson-Brown, illustrator of Greek Myth Comix and teacher, Churcher's College

Chair: Will Griffiths, Hands Up Education

Panel 60 – Gendered Violence in Early Christianity: round-table discussion

Lecture Block 4

Blossom Stefaniw, MF Norwegian School of Theology, Religion and Society [online]

Jennifer Barry, University of Mary Washington [online]

Ellen Muehlberger, University of Michigan [online]

Kathy L. Gaca, Vanderbilt University [online]

Chair: Victoria Leonard, Institute of Classical Studies and Centre for Arts, Memory and Communities, Coventry University

Panel 61 – Cambridge Elements on Women in the History of Philosophy: book series launch

Lecture Block 5

Writing 'Pythagorean Women'

Caterina Pellò, University of Nottingham [online]

Writing 'Platonist and Neoplatonist Women'

Crystal Addey, University College Cork

Writing 'Early Christian Women'

Dawn LaValle Norman, Australian Catholic University

Chair: James Warren, University of Cambridge

Panel 62 – Teaching Greek and Latin

Room G.19

Does studying Latin make you smarter?

Alexandra Vereeck, Ghent University

Ten years of OCR entry-level Latin and St John Rigby College – a case study in inclusivity

Anastacia Holding, St John Rigby Sixth Form College

Teaching Greek as Greek, not Latin: indefiniteness

Katharine Radice, Parkside Community College

Chair: Charles Weiss, University of Cambridge

Panel 63 – History and Myth in the Classroom

Room G.21

The Minotaur in the cave: San rock art in a Classics curriculum

Helen Lenahan, University of KwaZulu-Natal

Modern myths, ulterior motivations: applying Classical mythology to politics in the classroom

Jerome Ruddick, Newcastle University

Slavery in the classroom: using children's novels to explore Roman Britain

Emily Bassaly, Bedford School

Chair: Tim Morrison, Rugby School and University of Birmingham

Panel 64 – Connecting Objects and People: the Classical Collections Network

Room 1.02

The Classical Collections Network: building a network, engaging the public

Vicky Donnellan, British Museum

'Go figure!' Using a cast collection to tackle body image with teenagers

Susanne Turner, University of Cambridge, and Arlene Holmes-Henderson, Durham University

Swastikas and skull-measuring at Schliemann's first exhibition and what it means for us today

Abi Baker, Fitzwilliam Museum

Everyone's past: empowering communities to reshape the Ancient Worlds gallery in Leeds City Museum

Kat Baxter, Leeds Museums and Galleries

Chair: Anna Reeve, University of Leeds

6:00pm-6:45pm: *Reception for Teachers*
MOCA Cast Gallery

6:15pm – 6:45pm: **Classical Association AGM**
Lady Mitchell Hall

6:45pm: **Presidential Address**
Lady Mitchell Hall

MM McCabe, University of Cambridge and King's College London

7:30pm: *Drinks Reception for those attending the Conference*
Dinner
Newnham College

8:00pm: **Conference Dinner and Prizegiving Ceremony**
Newnham College

This event will feature the awarding of the Classical Association Prize and Teaching Awards.

DAY 3: Sunday 23 April 2023

9:00am – 11:00am: **Panel Session 8**

Panel 65 – Violence, Victims and Adjuncts in Greek Tragedy

Little Hall

Voices of victimhood in Euripides' Hecuba

Natasha Ferreira, Stellenbosch University and University of Pretoria

Re-examining the language of sexual violence in Greek literature

Suzanne Lynch, University College Dublin

Rape or marriage? The language of sexual violence in Greek tragedy

Kirsty Harrod, Coventry University

Plot-changers: the minor roles in Greek tragedy

Georgina Homer, Coventry University

Chair: Nancy Rabinowitz, Hamilton College

Panel 66 – British School at Athens Fieldwork

Lecture Block 1

Rapid urbanisation in ancient Olynthos: some challenges to twentieth-century perceptions of ancient city building

Zosia Archibald, University of Liverpool

Invisible economies of ancient west Samos

Jana Mokrišová, University of Cambridge [online]

Beyond Keros: investigating a maritime territory in the central Cyclades

Michael Boyd, McDonald Institute [online]

Chiona-East Beach excavation and underwater mapping at Palaikastro, Crete

Andrew Shapland, Ashmolean Museum, University of Oxford

Chair: Georgios Mouratidis, British School at Athens [online], and Michael Loy, British School at Athens and University of Cambridge

Panel 67 – Is That Latin? Some Perspectives on Variation and Innovation in Latin Linguistics

Lecture Block 2

-es and -aes: chicken or egg?

Rhiannon Smith, University of Cambridge

What kind of Latin is that? The place of hyperbaton in Latin prose

Agnes Vendel, University of Cambridge

A reduction in linguistic innovation: on Ovid's decreased use of Greek vocabulary in exile

Sólveig Hilmarsdóttir, University of Cambridge

Vocabula quaedam barbara: judgements on Latinity from Marius Nizzolius (1498-1566)

Josey Wright, University of Cambridge

Chair: Nicholas Zair, University of Cambridge

Panel 68 – Decolonising Classics in the Secondary School Classroom: a Discussion

Lecture Block 3

Where were we and what needed to change?

Katharine Radice, Parkside Community College

Who gets taught Classics? The benefits of introducing Classics in a non-traditional context

Stephanie Hamman, Eden Girls' School, Coventry

Classics as an engine for challenging colonialism

Alastair Thorley, Stockport Grammar School

Classics as a 'safe space'

Anna McOmish, Aldridge School [online]

Chair: Katharine Radice, Parkside Community College

Panel 69 – Precarious Classical Legacies: Unravelling the Use of Classics in Politics around the World (Session 1)

Lecture Block 5

The appropriation and deployment of Classics in socio-political discourse in contemporary Zimbabwe

Obert Bernard Mlambo, University of Zimbabwe and Rhodes University [online]

'Graecomania': the origins and reception of Mao's political metaphor

Zilong Guo, Northeast Normal University

The two tombs of Alexander the Great: broadcasting Classical Antiquity as national legacy in the Hellenic Republic

Manolis Pagkalos, University of Groningen [online], and Stefanos Apostolou, University of Nottingham [online]

Chair: Carol Atack, University of Cambridge

Panel 70 – New Perspectives on Elections and Electoral Competition in the Last Decades of the Roman Republic

Room G.19 – NB: This panel will continue until 11:30am.

The praerogativa centuria after Sulla and before Caesar

Giuseppe Zecchini, Università Cattolica di Milano [online]

Learning from defeat: what do accounts of electoral defeats tell us about Roman politics and society?

Alexander Yakobson, Hebrew University of Jerusalem

Catiline's electoral campaigns in 64 and 63 BC: new insights

Luca Fezzi, Università degli Studi di Padova

Consular elections in the post-Sullan decade: ideological conflict or response to social needs?

Eleonora Zampieri, Università degli Studi di Padova

Electoral bribery and political solidarity at the time of the lex Licinia: a new senatus consultum

Andrea Frizzera, Università degli Studi di Padova and Università Ca' Foscari, Venice

Chair: John Patterson, University of Cambridge

Panel 71 – Effective Approaches to Widening Participation

Room G.21

Sarah Scott, University of Leicester

Will Wootton, King's College London

Elena Theodorakopoulos, University of Birmingham

Chairs: Hilary Hodgson, Classics for All, and Hannah Walsh, Classics for All [online]

Panel 72 – Pyrrhus of Epirus: Images of Pyrrhus and of the Pyrrhic Wars**Room 1.02**

The wrath of the goddess: Pyrrhus' despoliation of Persephone's sanctuary at Lokri
Rolf Strootman, Utrecht University [online]

Death in Argos: Pyrrhus' last campaign and death scene as portrayed by Plutarch
Eran Almagor, Jerusalem

Pyrrhus' political propaganda in Sicily
Elena Santagati, Università degli Studi di Messina

Another Trojan War? Pyrrhic propaganda and Roman reinvention
Daniel Etches Jones, University of Oxford

Chair: Carlo Lualdi, University of Warwick, and Daniel Etches Jones, University of Oxford

Panel 73 – Greek Comedy: Joking Aside**Room 1.11**

Political theory with Aristophanes
Megan Bowler, University of Oxford

The limit of humour: scholiastic approaches to a hubristic joke in Aristophanes' Frogs
Amy Lewis, University of Pennsylvania and Howard University

Diversity and identity in comic choruses
Daniel Anderson, Coventry University

The manly tragic woman and the effeminate comedic man: subversion of gender categories in Orestes and Thesmophoriazousae
Alex MacFarlane, University of Birmingham

Chair: James Robson, Open University

11:00am – 11:30am: *Break (refreshments)*

11:30am – 12:30pm: **Plenary Lecture**
Lady Mitchell Hall

Classics in the 2020s: goblin mode and beyond
Tim Whitmarsh, University of Cambridge

12:30pm – 1:30pm: **Photography Exhibition Reception and Prizegiving**

12:30pm – 1:30pm: *Lunch (provided on-site)*

1:30pm – 3:30pm: **Panel Session 9**

Panel 74 – Roman Epic

Little Hall

Fear, power and agency: the tyrant figure in Valerius Flaccus and Statius

Dalida (Lili) Agri, University of Manchester

Pyrrhus' perverted paraclausithyron in Aeneid 2

Tom Nelson, University of Oxford

Parent trees in Virgil's Aeneid

Katie Woods-Williams, University of Exeter

Dreams in Roman epic: the oneiric poetics of Lucretius, Virgil and Ovid and their implications for political discourse

Fernando Martinez-Periset, Stanford University [online]

Chair: Ludovico Pontiggia, University of Cambridge

Panel 75 – Different Approaches to Classical Reception from Antiquity to the Twentieth Century

Lecture Block 1

Oratorum pinakes: clues to Classical orators' reception in medieval and modern Greek codices

Lorenzo Sardone, Università degli Studi di Cassino e del Lazio Meridionale [online]

The Περὶ Ὑψους between philology and counter reformation: editions, translations and unpublished commentaries

Olivia Montepaone, Università degli Studi di Milano

Reframing Leopardi's interest in fifth-century Latin authors

Giulia Marolla, Università degli Studi di Bari

Rocco Scotellaro's poetry between popular and Classical traditions

Roberta Berardi, University of Oxford

Chair: Sharon Marshall, University of Exeter

Panel 76 – Jewish-Greek Culture in Antiquity (in memoriam Professor James Aitken)

Lecture Block 2

Josephus's rhetorical skill in Against Apion

David Friedman, University of Cambridge

Language in Roman Caesarea

Shoni Lavie-Driver, University of Cambridge

The cultural politics of wonder in the Letter of Aristeas

Max Leventhal, University of Cambridge

Chair: Lea Niccolai, University of Cambridge

Panel 77 – Plato and Community in Cambridge and Ghana

Lecture Block 3

Plato and community in Cambridge and Ghana

Frisbee Sheffield, University of Cambridge

Plato's Republic V: a re-reading from an Afro-Communitarian perspective

Michael K. Okyere Asante, University of Environmental and Sustainable Development and Stellenbosch University

How can partners be slaves? Rethinking politics in Plato's Republic

Stephen O. Peprah, Girton College, Cambridge

Plato the enemy and Aristotle the ally

James Warren, University of Cambridge

Chair: Rosanna Omitowoju, University of Cambridge

Panel 78 – Two Cultures? Conscious and Unconscious Paradigms in Classics and Archaeology

Lecture Block 4 – NB: This panel will begin at 1:00pm and continue until 4:00pm.

Turning to the material and environmental: how can we make the most of material and environmental paradigms in Classics?

Lin Foxhall, University of Liverpool

Teaching paradigms: Classical Archaeology courses at German-speaking universities in the twenty-first century

Matthias Hoernes, University of Vienna

Intellectual silos? Citation networks in British Classical Archaeology

Michael Loy, British School at Athens and University of Cambridge

Plus ça change? What Classical Archaeology is for

Ian Morris, Stanford University

Graphein: text and image between Classics and Archaeology

Eliza Scholz, University of Cambridge

'Choice item though this is, it hardly tells us anything we did not already know' (Hornblower)

James Whitley, Cardiff University

Chair: Michael Squire, University of Cambridge

Panel 79 – Precarious Classical Legacies: Unravelling the Use of Classics in Politics Around the World (Session 2)

Lecture Block 5

Classics in the press: articles of Colombian President and Latinist Miguel Antonio Caro
Gemma Bernardó Ferrer, Universidad de los Andes [online]

The role of Tyrtaeus' martial elegy in shaping patriotic nationalism in early independent Mexico and beyond

Bernardo Berruecos Frank, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México [online]

Tacit Classical overtones: anti-democratic discourse in contemporary Brazil

Breno Battistin Sebastiani, University of São Paulo [online]

Chair: Shushma Malik, University of Cambridge

Panel 80 – #WCCWiki Roundtable: Teaching Classics with Wikipedia

Room G.19

Supporting staff and students as university Wikipedian in Residence, and on the Wikimedia in Education programme

Ewan McAndrew, University of Edinburgh

Wikipedia in teaching: research using Wikipedia to explore issues of authorship, authority and the writing of history

Juliana Bastos Marques, Federal University of the State of Rio de Janeiro [online]

Wikipedia editing in an undergraduate course on Roman Britain

Victoria Austen, Carleton College [online]

Setting Wikipedia editing assignments as part of undergraduate Classics courses

Chelsea Gardner, Acadia University

Wikipedia and history in schools

Nadege Forde, Sankofa Project

Wikipedia editing at museum events

Lucy Moore, University of York and Leeds Museums and Galleries [online]

Facilitators: Katharine Shields, KCL and #WCCWiki, Victoria Leonard, Coventry University and #WCCWiki, and Anna Judson, Durham University and #WCCWiki

Panel 81 – Pyrrhus of Epirus: Military Aspects of the Pyrrhic Wars

Room 1.02

Pyrrhus' tactics in Italy: a critical review

Carlo Lualdi, University of Warwick

The Mamertines and the outbreak of the Pyrrhic Wars

Fernando López Sánchez, Complutense University of Madrid [online]

Pyrrhus, Fabricius, an elephant, and the Roman POWs: Roman reception of their own legend

Gaius Stern, UC Berkeley and San Jose State University [online]

Chair: Eran Almagor, Jerusalem

Panel 82 – Emancipatory and Reflective Pedagogies in the Teaching of Classical Antiquity

Room 1.11 – NB: This panel will begin at 1:00pm and continue until 4:00pm.

Functional multilingual learning of ancient languages at primary school: a valuable transformative learning tool

Evelien Bracke, Ghent University [online]

'Opening up a world ...': how and why Classical myth resonates with being autistic

Susan Deacy, Bristol and Leicester University [online]

Transforming students' thinking skills through the new Classics curriculum in Greece

Marisa Fountopoulou, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens [online], and Dr Effrosyni Kostara, Hellenic Open University – Greek Institute of Educational Policy

Using progressive feedback in teaching Classics and Ancient History: a case study on Neronian literature

Andreas Gavrielatos, University of Reading

Our mythical childhood: new resources on- and offline for outreach, pedagogy and engagement

Katarzyna Marciniak, University of Warsaw [online], and Sonya Nevin, University of Cambridge

Teaching cultural heritage: Classics at Ibadan 1948-

Olakunbi Olasope, University of Ibadan, Nigeria [online]

Chairs: Fiona McHardy, University of Roehampton, and Effrosyni Kostara, Hellenic Open University – Greek Institute of Educational Policy